

Research Article

Pattern of Consumption of Quails and Quail Products in Lafia North Development Area of Nasarawa State

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Abstract

This study examined the pattern of consumption of quails and quail product in Lafia North development area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. A total of 50 respondents were randomly sampled for this study. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. This study revealed that majority of the respondents were youth aged between 21 – 30 years with the percentage of 40 and are married. This study further revealed that majority forty two percent of the respondents have tertiary education and sixty four percent were male. The mean and standard deviation of the socio-economic characteristics are Age (1.60±1.12), gender (0.36±0.48), marital status (0.78±0.74), educational level (2.72±1.07), occupation (0.40±0.74) and Household size (0.58±0.88) respectively. Thirty two percent of the respondents affirmed that radio programmes were the major source of information on the nutritional value of quail and quail products while eight percent affirmed that pamphlet is the only source of information on the nutrient values of quail products. Forty six and thirty eight percent of the respondents preferred fried meat and half boiled eggs while twenty percent of the farmers preferred gravy (sauce) and raw egg. Thirty eight percent of the respondents consumed meat and eggs twice a week while eighteen percent consumed meat and eggs once a week. The highest consumption rate for meat (kg) and number of eggs were forty eight percent (1 – 2kg) and (1 – 9) while the lowest consumption rate for meat and eggs by the farmers are lack of information on nutritional quality of quail. In line with this findings, it is recommended that further enlightenment is required especially for the female respondents on the nutritional benefits of quail and quail products.

Keywords: Pattern, quails, consumption, respondent and products.

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Introduction

In Nigeria, chicken appears to be the most common of all the avian species. However alternative source of high quality meat and egg within a relative shorter time and cheaper cost has now been found in the Japanese quail.

Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) is becoming more popular as a source of meat and eggs in various parts of the world.

Japanese quail has marked advantages such as its fast growth, early sexual maturity, high rate of egg production, short generation interval and short incubation period (Panda and Singh, 1990; Reddish *et al.*, 2003). Under favourable environment, quail hen can lay up to 280-300 eggs in their first year (Metin and Serdal, 2004). Thus quail has an excellent potential to serve as an excellent and cheap source of animal protein for Nigeria (NVRI, 1996).

Quail a member of the galliformes order is considered a very promising micro poultry farming species for rural and urban development because it requires little capital, equipment, space and labour and provides an inexpensive, readily available and high quality meat and eggs (NRC, 1991). From prehistoric time, it has been raised for food in Japan and America. Quails are now also reared for meat and eggs in different countries of America, Asia and Africa. Although quail farming contribute to the alleviation of protein deficiency in diets of people in developing countries, they have largely been neglected as a livestock species due to its size. Most farmers have focused mainly on chicken production. Thus, their actual contributions to healthy food production have been greatly ignored and or underestimated by extension and other development workers, and policy makers in the agricultural sector in developing countries (Owen and Amakiri, 2010).

A person's daily protein intake should be about 1kg/body weight for adequate nutrition and ideally 30 – 50% of the daily protein intake should be of animal origin in order to provide an optimal range of essential amino acid apart from vitamin B and iron. Average animal protein intake in developing countries is only 15g compared to 60g in developed countries. Expert committee of ICMR has recommended 60g of protein per day with net protein utilization of 5g.

The livestock and livestock products consumption pattern are the deciding factor for the development of livestock sector in general and a specific enterprise in particular.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to determine the pattern of consumption of quails and quail product in Lafia North development Area of Nasarawa State.

The specific objectives of the study are to;

- (i) Describe the socio-economic characteristics of the farmers
- (ii) Determine the level of awareness of the nutritional value of quail and quail products

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- (iii) Examine the consumption pattern of quail and quail product in the study area
- (iv) Determine the factor limiting quail and quail product consumption
- (v) Identify the information sources on the nutritional value of quails and quail production in the study area.

Materials and Method

Study Location

This study was carried out in Lafia North Development Area of Nasarawa State. The areas include Shabu, Ombi II and Azuba. The area lies within Latitude 8.33⁰N and Longitude 8.33⁰E at altitude 181.35m above sea level. The area is within the Guinea savanna zone of Nigeria with an average rainfall of 1182mm annually (NIMET, 2010).

The main occupation of the people were farming. The soil structure of the area is sandy loam which is suitable for agricultural practices.

The crops grown include yam, benniseed, groundnut, cowpea etc. The major tribes in the area include; Eggon, Akye, Alago, Migili, Rindre, Gwandara to mention but few (Lafia Local Government Information Unit, 2006).

Sampling Techniques

A total of 50 respondents were selected using simple random sampling techniques. Twenty farmers were sampled from Shabu, 15 farmers from Ombi II and 15 farmers from Azuba respectively.

Data Collection

The data required for this study were collected through the use of a structured questionnaire which were administered to the respondents. Data were collected on the socio-economic characteristic of the respondents, pattern of consumption of quails and quail products (meat and Eggs), preparation preference, sources of information on Quail's quality and the constraints to quail and quail products consumption respectively.

Data Analysis

The data obtained from this study were subjected to descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, mean, standard error and standard deviation using statistical packages for social science (SPSS 20.0) to achieve the study objectives.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of farmers

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
below 20	7	14
21 – 30	20	40
31 – 40	13	26
41 – 50	6	12
51 – 60	4	8
Total	50	100
Gender		
Male	32	64
Female	18	36
Total	50	100
Marital status		
Single	20	40
Married	21	42
Divorce	9	18
Total	50	100
Educational qualification		
Adult education	2	4
Primary school	5	10
Secondary education	10	10
Tertiary education	21	20
Illiterate	12	24
Total	50	100
Occupation		
Farming	30	60
Non-farming	20	40
Total	50	100
Household size		
0 – 8	30	60
9 – 17	14	28
18 – 26	4	8
27 – 35	1	2
Above 35	1	2
Total	50	100

Source: Field survey, 2015

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the socio-economic characteristics of the farmers

Variables	Mean	Standard deviation	Standard error
Age	1.60	1.12	0.16
Gender	0.36	0.48	0.07
Marital status	0.78	0.74	0.10
Education level	2.72	1.07	0.15
Occupation	0.40	0.49	0.07
Household size	0.58	0.88	0.12

Source: field survey, 2015

Table 3: Source of information on the nutritional value of quails and quail product.

Source of Information	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Radio programmes	16	32
Health workers	8	16
Television	14	28
Pamphlet	4	8
Newspaper	8	16
Total	50	100

Source: Field survey, 2015

Table 4: Preparation preference for quail and quail products

Preparation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Meat		
Fried	23	46
Gravy (Sauce)	10	20
Raw	17	34
Total	50	100
Egg		
Fried	4	8
Full boiled	17	34
Half boiled	11	38
Raw	10	20
Total	50	100

Source: Field survey, 2015

Table 5: Pattern of consumption of quail products

Meat and eggs	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Once in a week	9	18
Twice in a week	12	24
trice in a week	19	38
more than trice week	10	20
Total	50	100

Source: Field survey, 2015

Table 6: Quantity of quails and quail products consumed

Quail products	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Quantity of meat consumed(kg)		
1 – 2	24	48
3 – 4	16	32
5 – 6	6	12
7 – 8	2	4
9 – 10	2	4
Total	50	100
Number of eggs consumed		
1 – 9	30	60
10 – 19	13	26
20 – 29	4	8
30 – 39	2	4
Above 39	1	2
Total	50	100

Source: Field survey, 2015

Table 7: Factors limiting pattern of consumption of quail product

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lack of information on nutritional quail/quail products	24	48
Inadequate supply of quail product	12	24
High preference for chicken	6	12
Inadequate income of quail farmer	8	16
Total	50	100

Source: Field Survey, 2015

Socio-economic characteristics

Table 1. The result showed that, the majority of the farmers are within the age range of 21 – 30 years with a percentage of 40. The result revealed that 64% of the majority of the respondent are male with a frequency of 32. Majority of the farmers are married with a percentage of 42 while the highest number of farmers have tertiary education with 42%. The highest household size was between (0 – 8) with a percentage of 60 respectively.

It is evident that the majority of rural poultry keepers in the study area were adults in their active working age. This implies that poultry keeping is done by active men and women in the study area. Men have been reported to be the major producer of rural quails in the study area and it disagree

with the report of Nwanta *et al.* (2006), which states that Women have been reported to be the major producer of rural poultry in African societies.

The descriptive statistics of the socio-economic characteristic of the respondent.

Table 2. The mean and the standard deviation for Age, Gender, Marital status, Educational level, occupation and household size as thus: 1.60 ± 1.12 (Age), 0.36 ± 0.48 (Gender), 0.78 ± 0.74 (Marital status), educational level (2.72 ± 1.07), occupation (0.40 ± 0.49) and household size (0.58 ± 0.88) respectively. The standard error for Age, Gender, Marital status educational level, occupation and household size are 0.16, 0.07, 0.10, 0.15, 0.07, 0.12 respectively.

Source of information on the nutritional value of quails and quail products.

Table 3. The result revealed that 32% of the information about nutritional value of the quail products comes from radio programmes, 28% from television whereas only 8% comes from pamphlet while 96% from both Health workers and newspaper. It is evident that majority of the information about nutritional value of quails and quail product comes from radio programme as reported by Lalwani (2011) that the nutritional value of quail eggs is much higher than those offered by other eggs and they are rich sources of antioxidants, minerals, and vitamins, and give us a lot of nutrition than do other foods. Good nutrition affects growth and development of human body. Nutritional composition research has shown that eating well-balanced food can improve human health. A report by Wahab (2002) indicated that quail meat is an ideal food as authenticated in the Holy Bible and the Holy Koran and has no religious taboos.

Preparation preference for quails and quail products

Table 4. The result revealed that 46% of the respondent preferred fried meat, 34% choose raw meat while only 20% shows preference for gravy (sauce) meat. The result also revealed that for egg products 38% preferred half boiled egg, 34% preferred full boiled, 8% fried while only 8% preferred fried egg.

Consumption pattern of quail products.

Table 5. The result revealed that majority of the respondents (38%) consumed meat and eggs trice in a week, 24% consumed twice a week, 20% consumed more than trice week while only 18% consumed once a week.

The consumption of quail eggs fortifies the woman's body during pre and post-natal periods as well as after surgery and radiotherapy. It also has beneficial effects on the foetus (physical and mental balance) and for the mother after delivery (physical rehabilitation and rejuvenation of cells). Quail eggs also improve the quality of breast milk. Quail meat is tastier than chicken and has less fat content. It promotes body and brain development in children. Most of the developing countries are presently at a stage of perpetual protein hunger.

The high rate of returns and low cost of investment in the production of quail meat and egg are some of the reasons many farmers especially in the north are fast resorting to quail farming. The fact that the birds grow and reach maturity stage faster and lay eggs within two months, compared with the 6months maturity period of chicken for whether egg-laying or consumption will attract farmers who see the business as a better and more sustainable investment to explore.

Quantity and number of meat and eggs consumed weekly in kilogrammes.

Table 6 revealed that 48% of the respondents consumed between 1 – 2kg of meat while the least (4%) of respondent consumed between 7 – 8 and 9 – 10(kg) of meat respectively. While the highest number 60% of respondent consumed between 1 – 9 eggs per week while the least 2% consumed only above 39 eggs weekly. From this study it is revealed that majority of respondent consumed 1-9eggs per week.

Factors limiting consumption pattern of quails and quail products.

Table 7 also revealed that, 48% of the respondents affirmed that lack information on the nutritional value of quail products is the major limiting factor to consumption whereas 24% of respondents assumed that inadequate supply of quail products is the factor limiting consumption. Twelve percent of respondent said high preference for chicken while 16% of respondent state that inadequate income of quail farmers are the limiting factor to the consumption of quails and quail products. Therefore from this study it is evident that lack of information on the nutritional value of quails limit consumption.

Conclusion

The consumption of quail and quail products in the study area is relatively high and the major constraints to quail and quail product consumption is the lack of information on the nutritional benefit of quail. In spite of the exceptional attributes and advantages of keeping quail, its production is still comparatively rudimentary. The solution to the problem of inadequate consumption of quail by an average Nigeria is to increase the level of highly reproductive quails with short generation interval.

Recommendation

This study revealed that encouraging quail production in the study area will not only augment the present deficient animal protein intake but will deepen our understanding of these birds that are going popularity among farmers and various laboratories. Hence, farmers should invest heavily in rearing this species of poultry in Nigeria.

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